

MEDICAL SCIENCES

A RARE CASE OF IDIOPATHIC RETROPERITONEAL FIBROSIS

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ABSTRACT

Retroperitoneal Fibrosis (RPF) is a rare fibroinflammatory disorder characterized by the deposition of fibrous tissue in the retroperitoneal space, often involving the abdominal aorta, iliac arteries, and ureters¹. Despite its rarity, RPF can lead to significant morbidity, with limited epidemiological data available to guide clinical management. Here, we present the case of an 82-year-old female patient diagnosed with RPF, presenting with gross hematuria as the primary complaint. Our patient's clinical course was complicated by the atypical localization of fibrotic tissue, resulting in diagnostic challenges and necessitating a multidisciplinary approach to management. We discuss the diagnostic workup, including imaging studies, as well as the therapeutic interventions employed, such as corticosteroid therapy and interventional management. This case underscores the importance of considering RPF in the differential diagnosis of patients presenting with renal and urinary tract symptoms, particularly in older adults. By sharing our experience, we aim to contribute to the collective knowledge base and improve the care of future patients with this rare condition.

Keywords: Retroperitoneal Fibrosis; hematuria.

Introduction

Retroperitoneal Fibrosis, initially described by Ormond in 1948, is also commonly referred to as Ormond's disease. Limited epidemiological studies have been conducted, revealing an incidence rate ranging from 0.1 to 1.3 cases per 100,000 persons per year^{2,3,4}. This condition can be categorized into primary (idiopathic) and secondary forms associated with malignancies, medications, infections, and asbestos exposure^{5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12}. Approximately 70% of cases are idiopathic, presenting either in isolation or concomitantly with other autoimmune or IgG4-related diseases¹³. The pathogenesis is thought to involve a fibroinflammatory response, as evidenced by elevated acute phase reactants and autoantibodies.

The primary diagnostic modalities for Retroperitoneal Fibrosis (RPF) include contrast-enhanced computed tomography (CT) or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), while biopsy remains the most precise method for definitive diagnosis^{5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12}.

The primary objective of treating Retroperitoneal Fibrosis is to alleviate symptoms, prevent complications, impede progression, and minimize recurrence. Despite ongoing trials, glucocorticoids remain the primary therapy of choice. Approximately 75-90% of patients respond to glucocorticoid therapy alone. For patients with unfavorable outcomes, combination therapy

with alternative immunosuppressants such as rituximab, methotrexate, or mycophenolate mofetil may be utilized¹⁴. Unfortunately, the available data on the efficacy of these alternative drugs predominantly stem from small case series.

Case presentation

In January of 2023, an 83-year-old female presented to the hospital with the primary complaint of gross hematuria. The patient's medical history was largely unremarkable, aside from managed hypertension and type 2 diabetes mellitus, for which she was undergoing treatment with antihypertensive medications and metformin, respectively. Initial diagnostic considerations centered around ureterolithiasis; however, renal ultrasonography yielded negative results for calculi. Laboratory investigations revealed a creatinine level of 96.74 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ and a glomerular filtration rate (GFR) of 47, alongside notable findings of red blood cells (RBCs) in urinalysis. Following this presentation, the patient experienced no further episodes of hematuria and was lost to follow-up.

In May of 2023, the patient was readmitted to the hospital, reporting a recurrence of gross hematuria with heightened frequency. Subsequent magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) revealed the presence of a periureteral retroperitoneal mass on the right side, concomitant with observed hydronephrosis of the right kidney.

Image 1: Coronal section of the abdominal cavity showing T1 and T2 imaging reveals a retroperitoneal infiltrative mass in the right ureteral region, which encases blood vessels and narrows the calibers of the inferior vena cava and renal veins. Right-sided hydronephrosis is also noted.

Image 2: Sagittal section with T1 and T2 post-contrast imaging shows a retroperitoneal mass infiltrating the right ureter and the right uterine wall.

Radiologically and symptomatically, no evidence suggestive of malignancy was observed, leading to the diagnosis of idiopathic retroperitoneal fibrosis. The initial investigative approach aimed at ruling out secondary etiologies of retroperitoneal fibrosis, considering the absence of significant medical history such as malignancies, smoking history, radiation exposure, medication or asbestos exposure. Additionally, the negative result of the tuberculosis skin test further supported the exclusion of infectious etiologies. Biopsy was not performed due to the patient's preferences. However, assays for smooth muscle antibody (Ab), IgG4, kappa and lambda light chains, antinuclear antibody (ANA), double-stranded DNA antibody (dsDNA Ab), and antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA) were conducted, all of which yielded results within the normal range. Top of Form The patient disclosed a history of COVID-19 infection in 2020, followed by vaccination in the spring of 2021 and a subsequent booster dose one year later.

Laboratory assessments conducted at the time of diagnosis revealed a creatinine level of 91.99 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ and a glomerular filtration rate (GFR) of 53. Initiation of steroid therapy promptly followed diagnosis, starting with an initial dosage of 64 mg of methylprednisolone administered once daily. However, due to adverse effects, the dosage was subsequently reduced to 32 mg daily, and then further tapered to 16 mg daily. Initially, the patient experienced symptomatic relief with diminished hematuric episodes; however, in July of 2023, her clinical status deteriorated, manifesting as renal symptom recurrence, necessitating the placement of bilateral ureteral stents. Notably, her creatinine level surged to 317.13 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, accompanied by a GFR of 12. Subsequent MRI imaging delineated bilateral hydronephrosis secondary to fibrous masses on both sides.

In response to the exacerbation of symptoms, glucocorticoid dosage was augmented, supplemented by the introduction of micophenolate mofetil, resulting in symptomatic amelioration. Throughout August and September of 2023, the patient's clinical condition and laboratory parameters remained within acceptable bounds, prompting the continuation of the established therapeutic regimen. However, patient's health status declined precipitously in October of 2023, marked by acute renal failure, dyspnea, hypervolemia, hyperkalemia, and acidosis. Despite the initiation of hemodialysis and other life-saving interventions, the patient's clinical status failed to improve, culminating in cardiac asystole and subsequent demise within two days of hospital admission.

Discussion

Retroperitoneal fibrosis (RPF) is a relatively uncommon disorder characterized by diverse primary complaints¹⁵. It exhibits a male predominance, with a ratio ranging from 2:1 to 3:1^{5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12}, and typically manifests most frequently between the ages of 40 and 60, although onset can occur at any stage of life. The majority of idiopathic cases of RPF fall within the category of chronic periaortitis (CP), primarily localized in the peri-aortoiliac region, often presenting with vague abdominal discomfort¹⁶. However, the clinical

presentation of RPF lacks specificity and varies depending on the anatomical distribution of fibrous tissue. While dull abdominal pain is commonly reported, symptoms may also include lower back or flank pain, and more than half of affected males may experience testicular discomfort^{17,18}. Additional manifestations encompass fatigue, weight loss, fever, gastrointestinal disturbances, and lower limb edema, the latter often attributed to compression of the inferior vena cava or lymphatic vessels.

In cases where RPF affects the urinary tract and kidneys, patients may present with urinary symptoms such as frequency, urgency, and dysuria. Gross hematuria, although less common, can also occur. Ultrasound imaging may reveal unilateral or bilateral hydronephrosis and renal parenchymal atrophy, indicative of progressive ureteral obstruction or compromised renal perfusion secondary to arterial compression¹⁹.

Despite ongoing efforts, the pathogenesis of RPF remains elusive, with many suggesting it involves a fibroinflammatory response, evident through elevated acute phase reactants, autoantibodies, and a positive response to systemic glucocorticoid therapy. This multifactorial pathogenesis is influenced by environmental factors, with smoking and asbestos exposure playing significant roles²⁰. Genetically, the disease is primarily associated with HLA-DRB1*03, a marker of autoimmunity, suggesting an antigen-driven mechanism^{21,22,23,24}. One hypothesis proposes that antigen-presenting cells present antigens to CD4 T cells within the retroperitoneum, leading to the activation and secretion of IL-6. This, in turn, activates B cells and fibroblasts. The cytokines expressed by activated CD4 T cells may drive the maturation of B cells into plasma cells, preferentially resulting in the expansion of IgG4-producing plasma cells, explaining the association of retroperitoneal fibrosis with IgG4-related diseases^{25,26}. Like most immune-mediated conditions, there is no cure of IgG4-related diseases but it is very treatable. When organ damage occurs, it is usually due to delays in diagnosis and insidious development of organ involvement and damage following treatment-induced remission. While there is a strong association between IgG4-related diseases and retroperitoneal fibrosis, our patient exhibited normal IgG4 levels, thus challenging this theory.

Diagnosing RPF can pose significant challenges, yet magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and computed tomography (CT) scans serve as invaluable tools for assessing the extent of retroperitoneal fibrosis. A typical finding includes a retroperitoneal mass with homogeneous attenuation, enveloping the aorta, inferior vena cava, and deflecting ureters medially. For patients with iodinated contrast allergy or a decreased glomerular filtration rate, MRI is the most effective diagnostic tool²⁷. To accurately assess the extension of fibrous tissue in the retroperitoneum, the use of gadolinium is highly recommended. On MRI, RPF appears as a hypointense mass in T1-weighted images. In T2-weighted images, its intensity is high during the active phase of the disease, characterized by inflammation and tissue edema, and low during the quiescent phase²⁸. Biopsy remains a cornerstone for definitive diagnosis; microscopically,

biopsy specimens typically consist of type I collagen, fibroblasts, and myofibroblasts. The Inflammatory infiltrate primarily includes B and T lymphocytes, macrophages, plasma cells, and neutrophils arranged in a perivascular aggregate configuration. If the proportion of IgG4-positive plasma cells in the aggregate exceeds 30 to 40 percent, RPF is likely IgG4-related²⁹. Unfortunately, in our case, the patient declined this invasive procedure.

The primary objective of treating Retroperitoneal Fibrosis is to alleviate symptoms, prevent complications, hinder progression, and minimize recurrence. Definitive management of idiopathic RPF lacks evidence-based guidelines due to the scarcity of clinical trials. Nevertheless, glucocorticoids remain the cornerstone of therapy, with additional immunosuppressive agents such as azathioprine and mycophenolate mofetil being adjunctive options. Although treatment typically yields favorable outcomes in 75-90% of cases, unfortunately, our patient did not benefit from this approach. The subsequent management can be categorized into the following groups: treatment of urinary obstruction, treatment of vascular obstruction, and treatment of secondary diseases. In the case of urinary obstruction direct indications for intervention procedures include conditions such as moderate and severe hydronephrosis, mild hydronephrosis of the only kidney, or mild hydronephrosis with impaired kidney function. Various interventional approaches exist, with the most preferred being the insertion of indwelling ureteral stents³⁰. This approach requires minimal intervention and promotes the best possible quality of life. If stent placement is not feasible, more invasive procedures such as percutaneous nephrostomy or open surgery can be considered.

Regarding vascular obstruction, if the disease process involves large and medium-sized vessels, causing vascular compromise, percutaneous interventions such as angioplasty and stenting, in conjunction with systemic medical therapy, can be attempted³¹. If the disease recurs or the treatment proves ineffective, open surgery becomes the final option for management.

In cases where Retroperitoneal Fibrosis is a result of a secondary cause (e.g., drugs, malignancies, retroperitoneal hemorrhage, radiation therapy), the primary goal of treatment is directed towards addressing the underlying etiology. This may involve discontinuing of offending drug, which can improve symptoms within a few months. However, in the case of persistent disease manifestation, it is recommended to initiate glucocorticoid therapy^{32,33,34,35}.

The shortage of standardized management protocols underscores the importance of reporting cases like ours, as it contributes to the collective knowledge of this rare disease, ultimately facilitating expedited diagnosis and the development of more effective therapeutic strategies in the future.

References

1. Vaglio A, Salvarani C, Buzio C. Retroperitoneal fibrosis. *Lancet Lond Engl*. 2006;367(9506):241-251. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(06)68035-5
2. van Bommel EFH, Jansen I, Hendriksz TR, Aarnoudse ALHJ. Idiopathic retroperitoneal fibrosis:

prospective evaluation of incidence and clinicoradiologic presentation. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2009;88(4):193-201.

doi:10.1097/MD.0b013e3181afc420

3. Ormond JK. Bilateral ureteral obstruction due to envelopment and compression by an inflammatory retroperitoneal process. *J Urol*. 1948;59:1072-1079.

4. Izabela Łońa Monika Wieliczko Jacek Lewandowska Jolanta Małyszko. Kidney Blood Press Retroperitoneal Fibrosis Is Still an Underdiagnosed Entity with Poor Prognosis. *Kidney Blood Press Res*. 2022;47(3):151-162. doi: 10.1159/000521423.

5. Ranschaert E, ergerg e, Ranchod A, et al. Retroperitoneal fibrosis. Reference article, Radiopaedia.org (Accessed on 13 Jul 2024) <https://doi.org/10.53347/rID-14537>

6. Kermani TA, Crowson CS, Achenbach SJ et-al. Idiopathic retroperitoneal fibrosis: a retrospective review of clinical presentation, treatment, and outcomes. *Mayo Clin. Proc*. 2011;86 (4): 297-303. doi:10.4065/mcp.2010.0663 - Free text at pubmed - Pubmed citation

7. van Bommel EF, Jansen I, Hendriksz TR et-al. Idiopathic retroperitoneal fibrosis: prospective evaluation of incidence and clinicoradiologic presentation. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2009;88 (4): 193-201. doi:10.1097/MD.0b013e3181afc420 - Pubmed citation

8. Retroperitoneal Fibrosis Joshua S. Engelsgerd; Chad A. LaGrange. StatPearls Publishing; 2024 Jan.

9. Peng L, Zhang P, Li J, Liu Z, Lu H, Zhu L, IgG4-related aortitis/peri-aortitis and periarteritis: a distinct spectrum of IgG4-related disease. *Arthritis Res Ther*. 2020 May 4;22(1):103.

10. Urban ML, Palmisano A, Nicastro M, Corradi D, Buzio C, Vaglio A. Idiopathic and secondary forms of retroperitoneal fibrosis: a diagnostic approach. *Rev Med Interne*. 2015;36:15-21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.revmed.2014.10.008>.

11. Brandt AS, Kamper L, Kukuk S, et al. Associated findings and complications of retroperitoneal fibrosis in 204 patients: Results of a urological registry. *J Urol*. 2011;185:526-531.

12. Retroperitoneal fibrosis – the state-of-the-art Marta Runowska, corresponding author Dominik Majewski, and Mariusz Puszczewicz *Reumatologia*. 2016; 54(5): 256-263.

13. Bangolo AI, Gupta K, Atoot A. IgG4-Related Disease Retroperitoneal Fibrosis: An Unusual Cause of Low Back Pain. *Cureus*. Published online February 28, 2021. doi:10.7759/cureus.13608

14. Tanaka T, Masumori N. Current approach to diagnosis and management of retroperitoneal fibrosis. *Int J Urol*. 2020;27(5):387-394. doi:10.1111/iju.14218

15. Vaglio A, Salvarani C, Buzio C. Retroperitoneal fibrosis. *Lancet*. 2006;367:241-251. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(06)68035-5

16. Vaglio A, Maritati F. Idiopathic retroperitoneal fibrosis. *J Am Soc Nephrol*. 2016;27:1880-1889

17. Khosroshahi A, Carruthers MN, Stone JH, et al. Rethinking Ormond's disease: "idiopathic" retroperitoneal fibrosis in the era of IgG4-related disease. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2013;92:82. doi:10.1097/MD.0b013e318289610f

18. Retroperitoneal Fibrosis: Ormond's Disease, Low Urine Output. Cleveland Clinic. Accessed May 9, 2024. <https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/diseases/23168-retroperitoneal-fibrosis>
19. Sheth R, Malik D. Bilateral Hydronephrosis From Retroperitoneal Fibrosis. *Cureus*. Published online December 18, 2020. doi:10.7759/cureus.12147
20. Uibu T, Oksa P, Auvinen A, et al. Asbestos exposure as a risk factor for retroperitoneal fibrosis. *Lancet Lond Engl*. 2004;363(9419):1422-1426. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(04)16100-X
21. Martorana D, Márquez A, Carmona FD, et al. A large-scale genetic analysis reveals an autoimmune origin of idiopathic retroperitoneal fibrosis. *J Allergy Clin Immunol*. 2018;142(5):1662-1665. doi:10.1016/j.jaci.2018.06.045
22. I Lee. Human fibroblasts in idiopathic retroperitoneal fibrosis express HLA-DR antigens. *J Korean Med Sci*. 1991 Sep;6(3):279-83. doi:10.3346/jkms.1991.6.3.279.
23. Augusto Vaglio corresponding author and Federica Maritati. Idiopathic Retroperitoneal Fibrosis. *J Am Soc Nephrol*. 2016 Jul; 27(7): 1880–1889.
24. Davide Martorana, PhD. Ana Márquez, PhD. F. David Carmona, PhD. Francesco Bonatti, PhD. Alessia Adorni, PhD. Maria L. Urban, MD. Federica Maritati, MD. Eugenia Accorsi Buttini, MD. Chiara Marvisi, MD. Alessandra Palmisano, MD. Giovanni M. Rossi, MD. Giorgio Trivioli, MD. Paride Fenaroli, MD. Lucio Manenti, MD. Maria Nicastro, BSS. Monia Incerti, BSS. Davide Gianfreda, MD. Stefano Bani, MD. Stefania Ferretti, MD. Domenico Corradi, MD. Federico Alberici, MD, PhD. Giacomo Emmi, MD, PhD. Gerardo Di Scala, MD. Gabriella Moroni, MD. Antonio Percesepe, MD. Paul J. Scheel Jr., MD. Eric Vermeer, MD, PhD. Eric F. van Bommel, MD. Javier Martín, MD, PhD †. Augusto Vaglio, MD, PhD. A large-scale genetic analysis reveals an autoimmune origin of idiopathic retroperitoneal fibrosis. *JACI VOLUME 142, ISSUE 5, P1662-1665, NOVEMBER 2018*.
25. Ramshaw AL, Roskell DE, Parums DV. Cytokine gene expression in aortic adventitial inflammation associated with advanced atherosclerosis (chronic periaortitis). *J Clin Pathol*. 1994;47(8):721-727. doi:10.1136/jcp.47.8.721
26. Izabela Łońa Monika Wieliczko [Jacek Lewandowska Jolanta Małyszko], Retroperitoneal Fibrosis Is Still an Underdiagnosed Entity with Poor Prognosis, explaining the association of retroperitoneal fibrosis with IgG4-related diseases. *Kidney & Blood Pressure Research*, 2022, Vol 47, Issue 3, p151
27. Fenaroli P, Maritati F, Vaglio A. Into clinical practice: diagnosis and therapy of retroperitoneal fibrosis. *Curr Rheumatol Rep*. 2021;23(3):18. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11926-020-00966-9>.
28. Engelsgerd JS, LaGrange CA. Retroperitoneal Fibrosis. In: *StatPearls*. StatPearls Publishing; 2024. Accessed May 9, 2024. <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK482409/>
29. Razok A, Malik R, Cackamvalli P, Zahid M. IgG4 related disease as a cause of isolated retroperitoneal fibrosis with no other organ involvement; Case report. *Ann Med Surg*. 2021;61:69-72. doi:10.1016/j.amsu.2020.12.028
30. Mertens S, Zeegers AGM, Wertheimer PA, Hendriks TR, van Bommel EFH. Efficacy and complications of urinary drainage procedures in idiopathic retroperitoneal fibrosis complicated by extrinsic ureteral obstruction. *Int J Urol Off J Jpn Urol Assoc*. 2014;21(3):283-288. doi:10.1111/iju.12234
31. Hartung O, Alimi YS, Di Mauro P, Portier F, Juhan C. Endovascular treatment of ilio caval occlusion caused by retroperitoneal fibrosis: late results in two cases. *J Vasc Surg*. 2002;36(4):849-852.
32. Marcolongo R, Tavolini IM, Laveder F, Busa M, Noventa F, Bassi P. Immunosuppressive therapy for idiopathic retroperitoneal fibrosis: a retrospective analysis of 26 cases. *Am J Med*. 2004;116(3):194–7.
33. van Bommel EF, Siemes C, Hak LE, van der Veer SJ, Hendriks TR. Long-term renal and patient outcome in idiopathic retroperitoneal fibrosis treated with prednisone. *Am J Kidney Dis*. 2007;49:615–25. <https://doi.org/10.1053/j.ajkd.2007.02.268>.
34. Kardar AH, Kattan S, Lindstedt E, Hanash K. Steroid therapy for idiopathic retroperitoneal fibrosis: dose and duration. *J Urol*. 2002;168:550–5. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-5347\(05\)64677-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-5347(05)64677-0).
35. Scheel PJ Jr, Feeley N, Sozio SM. Combined prednisone and mycophenolate mofetil treatment for retroperitoneal fibrosis: a case series. *Ann Intern Med*. 2011;154:31–6. <https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-154-1-201101040-00005>.